

Country Perspectives on Improving Technical Assistance in the Health Sector

Kanagat N, Chauffour J, Ilunga JF, Yuma Ramazani S, Ovuoraye Ajiwohwodoma JJP, Ibrahim Anas-Kolo S, Maryjane O, Onuekwusi N et al. (2021). Gates Open Research.

Extended data— Re-Imagining Technical Assistance project interview guide

This interview guide was designed to help facilitate the interviews. Interviewers were encouraged to ask follow-up questions to obtain clarification, detail, or examples. Some questions were specific to the interviewee, their role, or the context of the interview.

The objective of the interviews with technical assistance (TA) actors was to uncover the opportunities and challenges around how TA was being designed and provided in the DRC and Nigeria. We were interested in TA actors' views on the TA models and principles they followed, lessons learned, and best practices. Questions were tailored slightly based on interviewee role, their institution, and their institution's role in the TA landscape i.e., whether they are a TA donor, funder, provider, or consumer.

At the start of each interview, interviewers obtained verbal consent of interviewees. Interviewees were informed that what they would share during the interview may be used in RTA products either in paraphrasing or direct quotation, but that any quote would be de-identified and no list of interviewees would be distributed or published.

1. Please give us your job title and describe your role.
2. What projects/initiatives are you currently involved in?
3. How are they funded?
4. Please talk us through your project - how was it funded, for how long, who designed it, how is implementation going?
5. How do you define TA?
 - a. What does TA mean to you?
 - b. What do you consider to be TA?
6. We are interested in the full spectrum of technical assistance.
 - a. What TA is coming from the government?
 - b. What TA is coming from donors?
 - c. How does TA get delivered?
7. How do international organizations come into [the DRC/Nigeria] and balance the objectives of international donors with local needs?
8. How is TA currently managed in [the DRC/Nigeria]?
 - a. Who manages TA?
 - b. Who is responsible for coordinating TA?
9. Who are the different stakeholders involved in TA?
10. What are current perceptions around TA?
11. How is TA evaluated?
 - a. Who evaluates it? How often?
12. How does accountability fit into the current TA mechanism?
 - a. Are there any structures in place currently to ensure accountability?
13. How does sustainability fit into the current TA mechanism?
14. [In Nigeria:] How does TA work at the state level?
15. [In the DRC]: What are your thoughts on the Inter-Donor Health Group (GIBS)?
16. When it comes to TA, what are the biggest challenges you face and what is working well?

17. What are the current challenges with how TA is designed and delivered?
18. What would you change to improve how TA is delivered?
19. Do you have any examples of successful partnerships between government and funders around TA?
20. How would you scale TA?
21. What is the key to success in your work? What contributes to the success of your work?
22. Which Ministry of Health initiatives have been successful in the past?
23. What are the key shifts that need to be worked on to modify the way TA is delivered and consumed?
 - a. What are some of the underlying principles that can be used to guide these shifts?
 - b. What will this change look like in practice?